

Linguistic discrimination in scientometrics^{*}

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Abstract. There is a severe lack of linguistic diversity in the most prominent databases that are currently available to compute impact metrics and other scientometric indicators. This can be observed in traditional citation indexes like Scopus and Web of Science, but also in newer services that provide altmetrics data like Altmetric and PlumX Metrics. We identify two major reasons for this lack of linguistic diversity. The first is the privileged status of English as the current lingua franca of scholarly communications. The second is the dominant role of a very limited number of organizations in the large-scale collection and redistribution of scientometrics data. In this position paper, we argue that such selection biases in scientometrics are discriminatory and thus prejudicial to the scholarly community, and especially to contributors who publish content and engage with other stakeholders using languages other than English. We then summarize our experience building Cobaltmetrics to show that there are no serious technical obstacles to the creation and operation of massively multilingual scientometric services.

Keywords: Scientometrics · Altmetrics · Linguistic diversity.

1 Selection biases and discrimination

Scientometrics—like any other kind of metrics and statistics—are a sampling game. The indicators and the metrics that can be extracted from scientometric databases are only as good as the underlying data collection processes. Although not everything that counts can be counted, and not everything that can be counted counts, scientometric data aggregators must strive to ensure that the samples they collect are representative of the populations they intend to analyze.

There is a strong tendency among the most prominent scientometric data aggregators to only or mostly collect data from English-language sources. This section summarizes the state of scientometrics with regards to linguistic diversity.

The documentation for Web of Science, a citation index now provided by Clarivate Analytics, states that “English is the universal language of science” and that “it is clear that the journals most important to the international research community are publishing full text in English” [13]. The selection process for journals and books further asserts that English-language content is “highly

^{*} Declared conflict of interest: the author is the chief executive officer of Thunken Inc., a corporation that owns and operates Cobaltmetrics.com, an altmetrics aggregator whose differentiation strategy hinges on the analysis of multilingual data sources.

desirable,” and that content in other languages is considered as long as English-language metadata can be provided [13,5,12]. Interestingly, the selection process for conference proceedings does not mention any linguistic preference [4]. Similarly, the documentation for Scopus, a citation index provided by Elsevier, claims that their database covers 40 languages while mentioning that “[t]he main language of the international scientific community—and therefore also for Scopus—is considered to be English. Therefore, all content of the records that are available in Scopus (title, abstract, keywords) need to be in English” [11,8,6]. The documentation does not mention a linguistic preference for the language of the citations. Moreover, Scopus and Web of Science both mention that cited references must use the Latin alphabet [13,6].

With regard to altmetrics, it is worth noting that not all indicators are sensitive to linguistic diversity. Tracking page views and download statistics, for example, is completely language independent. On the other hand, tracking citations in textual sources like Wikipedia or Twitter is, to a certain extent, language specific. Wikipedia is an interesting example: while Wikimedia releases free, public, uniform data dumps for Wikipedia editions in more than 200 languages [1], major altmetrics providers only include data from a limited number of languages. Altmetric, the leading altmetrics provider, tracks citations in English, Finnish, and Swedish Wikipedias [3]. PlumX Metrics, an altmetrics provider owned by Elsevier, tracks citations in the English, Portuguese, and Spanish editions [2].

English is the current lingua franca of scholarly communications. It also has the third largest community of first-language speakers with 378 million native speakers [7]. It is therefore expected that English-language data would be extensively represented in scientometric databases. The issue at hand is that the distribution of languages covered by scientometric databases is very dissimilar to the distribution of languages spoken and used by the scholarly community.

Smaller linguistic communities correlate with smaller market segments for organizations that depend on text mining and natural language processing and, thus, with lower profitability and return on investment for for-profit corporations. However, defining arbitrarily small lists of languages for which content is mined amounts to ignoring the attention that scholarly content receives in all other languages, without even collecting and analyzing the data. If and when author-level metrics are computed from such services, all researchers who publish, review, or comment using one or more ignored languages will necessarily receive under-estimated scores and rankings. We view such practices as discriminatory and unacceptable. The complex socioeconomic and geopolitical canvas of the scholarly community cannot be captured if linguistic diversity is disregarded.

2 Toward massively multilingual scientometrics

We started developing Cobaltmetrics to confirm that there are no serious technical obstacles to the creation and operation of massively multilingual scientometric services. Cobaltmetrics is an altmetrics aggregator that indexes citations in textual sources in more than 180 languages. Building the core features of

Cobaltmetrics, i.e. software to extract and normalize citations from text, required approximately 2 full-time equivalents for 6 months. Moreover, the vast majority of the languages we analyze are not spoken by any of the team members at Thunken.

Another reason why scientometric aggregators should embrace multilingualism is that citation data is now mostly machine-readable, thanks to advocacy efforts for citation standards and the use of persistent identifiers. In cases where references are not machine-readable, it is worth emphasizing that they can be described using local grammars or other comparable approaches. Full language models are not required to parse references as they follow a stricter, more compact, less ambiguous syntax. Restrictions on the scripts and writing systems used in references are also debatable considering that open-source transliteration algorithms are now readily available, among others from the Unicode Consortium, to convert any script to Latin if required. To rephrase the documentation for Web of Science, what is clear to us is that the journals most important to the international research community are publishing good research. Algorithmic complexity is not an excuse to disregard linguistic diversity.

Anglo-centrism and linguistic discrimination are prejudicial to science and to the scholarly community, and their consequences are not limited to scientometrics [10,9]. We appreciate and support initiatives like OpenCitations and Crossref Event Data that collect and remix scholarly data using processes that are language independent, and thus inherently massively multilingual.

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